

The Design Inspired by Phra Maha Chedi of King Rama I-IV at Wat Phra Chetuphon Vimolmangklaram Rajwaramahaviharn

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Abstract : The research will focus on creating pattern designs that are inspired by the pagodas, Phra Maha Chedi of King Rama I-IV, that are located in the temple, Wat Phra Chetuphon Vimolmangklaram Rajwaramahaviharn. Different aspects of the temple were studied, including the history, architecture, significance of the temple, and techniques used to decorate the pagodas, Phra Maha Chedi of King Rama I-IV. Moreover, composition of arts and the form of pattern designs which all led to the outcome of four Thai application pattern. The four patterns combine Thai traditional design with international scheme, however, maintaining the distinctiveness of the glaze mosaic tiles of each Phra Maha Chedi. The patterns consist of rounded and notched petal flowers, leaves and vine, and various square shapes, and original colors which are updated for modernity. These elements are then grouped and combined with new techniques, resulting in pattern designs with modern aspects and simultaneously reflecting the charm and the aesthetic of Thai craftsmanship which are eternally embedded in the designs.

Keywords : Chedi, Pagoda, pattern, Wat

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